
EFFECT OF HANDS-ON ACTIVITIES ON SKILLS ACQUISITION OF SENIOR SECONDARY CHEMISTRY STUDENTS IN PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of hands-on activities on skills acquisition of senior secondary chemistry students in physical chemistry. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design. A sample of 154 students from four purposively selected secondary schools out of a population of 1,643 SS II students from Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria was used for the study. The experimental group was taught physical chemistry using hands-on activities while the control group was taught using discussion method. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. A validated 25-item Physical Chemistry Skills Acquisition Test (PCSAT) was the instrument used to collect data. Reliability coefficients of 0.83 were established using Kuder-Richardson (KR-21). Mean and Standard Deviation scores were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses. The results indicated that students taught using hands-on activities had significantly higher mean skills acquisition scores than those taught using discussion method $F=191.004$, $P(0.0001<0.05)$. Male and female student in hands-on activities did not differ significantly in mean skills acquisition scores $F=138.172$, $P(0.071>0.05)$. It was recommended that teachers should be encouraged to adopt hands-on activities in teaching physical chemistry to enhance students' skills acquisition in physical chemistry.

Key words: hands-on activities, skills acquisition, physical chemistry.

Introduction

It is an obvious fact that no nation can develop scientifically and technologically if her citizenry are not properly directed. The problem with the nation education system is that learner is not properly taken care of in terms of skill acquisition by the emphasis placed on certification not minding the source and how much such certificate is obtained (Agogo, 2011). The nation's quest for science and technological advancement will become a mirage, if effective modality is not put in place to incorporate innovative methods that promote active

learning and considering the importance of chemistry in all round development, there is need to make sure that chemistry is properly taught most especially the difficult aspect such as physical chemistry using innovative methods such as hands-on activities.

Abudullai cited in Ogbeba and Ajayi (2016) describes hands-on activities as a method of teaching whereby students are engaged actively in class activities with the use of their hands and intellect under the guidance of the teacher. Ravishankar and Ladage (2009) describe hands-on activities as a teaching/ learning method is a situation where the learner uses his/her hands in carrying out activities that could enhance manipulative skills which the learner develops naturally. Acquisition of psychomotor skills for instance the effective handling of laboratory apparatus, chemicals, development of scientific thinking, identification of hazards along with having assess and control risk associated with chemicals (Ravishankar & Ladage, 2009). By implication, manipulative skills are activities which involve doing. These include accurate use of laboratory equipment, exposure to laboratory techniques, exposure to observational skills, ability to carry out simple tests/experiments, draw graphs, among others. Hands-on activities method tallies with the fourth objectives of National Policy of Education (FGN, 2013) which is acquisition of appropriate skills and competencies for the individual to live and contribute to the development of the society.

Skills acquisition as viewed by Adeyemo (2009) is a situation where a learner demonstrates competency in the manipulation skills, either by using his/her hands or other mechanical competencies. Thus, the emphasis here is hands-on activities. By implication, hands-on activities show that students have apparatus directly available for investigation.

Agogo and Ode (2011) describes functional education as the education for sustainable development that allowed the learner to acquire the right skills, capabilities, values and knowledge that foster responsible citizenship. By implication, practical or concrete activities

learnt are activities which involve doing using apparatus. These activities when properly apply in a lesson such as hands-on activities could enhance skills acquisition in such concepts such as physical chemistry taught conventionally in senior secondary schools.

In as much a lot of emphasis have been placed on students' skill acquisition and academic achievement in chemistry, achievement in the subject is still poor in external examinations such as Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) conducted by West African Examination Council and National Examination Council which had been traced to the use of conventional teaching method such as discussion method that does not put into consideration the students' activity in teaching and learning processes. Olorunyomi (2013) also noted that discussion method is popular in teaching/learning of SSCE physical Chemistry concept in Nigeria despite its limitations. The author added that discussion method is teacher-centered as it does not involve the learners enough participation and it may degenerate into mere talk and may be monopolized by few individuals. This may consequently lead to a conclusion far from the truth though such may be accepted by the group as a whole. In spite of the efforts of researchers to develop the scientific knowledge in our youths, research evidence in the past one decade were characterized by the use of discussion method which does not encourage skills acquisition.

Baiyelo and Adeyemo (2009) opined that skills acquisition can be seen as the application of knowledge, theory and skills students have developed during their lessons to complete real life tasks. Skills acquisition can be seen as an organized sequence of action learned through deliberate and systematic effort. Hofstein (2014) opines that meaningful learning is possible, if the students are given opportunities to manipulate equipment and materials in an environment suitable for them to construct their knowledge of phenomena and

related scientific concepts. The scholar was also of the view that appropriate practical activities can be effective in promoting cognitive skills, meta-cognitive skills and practical skills towards learning chemistry. By implication, it is clear that providing students with practical learning environment and thus to enhance students' skills acquisition.

However, the West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiner's report (2014/2015) on Chemistry result indicates that students are weak in some physical Chemistry concepts in the SSCE Chemistry syllabus such as chemical reactions, stoichiometry, ionic equations, redox reactions and ionic theory. The WAEC Chief Examiner's attributed the poor achievement of students to their unfamiliarity with the use of simple laboratory equipment, inadequate exposure to laboratory techniques, lack of observational skills, omission of units in calculated values, inability to write chemical equation correctly, assign correct charges to ions as well as inability to carry out simple calculations, carry out simple tests/experiments, draw graphs, among others. In this regard, it is clear that the poor achievement of male and female students in physical chemistry is a function of poor skills acquisition.

The differences between boys and girls in relation to chemistry achievement in respect of skills acquisition have received attention in recent years. While some studies showed that in general boys performed higher than the girls, other shows either; a no difference or those girls outperformed the boys. This assertion calls for examination of the effect of hands-on activities on skills acquisition of senior secondary chemistry student in physical chemistry.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. What is the difference in the mean skills acquisition scores between students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activities and those taught using discussion method?

2. What is the difference in the mean skills acquisition scores between male and female students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activities?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean skills acquisition scores between students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activities and those taught using discussion method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean skills acquisition scores between male and female students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activities.

Methodology

The purpose of the research was to examine the effect of hands-on activities on skills acquisition of senior secondary chemistry students in physical chemistry. The study adopts quasi experimental design. The study area was Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the 1,643 SSII students in the 31 granted aided schools. 154 students were purposively sampled from 4 of the schools that had some basic facilities and equipment in their laboratories. One instrument known as Physical Chemistry Skills Acquisition Test (PCSAT) was used to collect data for this study.

PCSAT is a 25-item multiple choice instrument that contains two sections. Section A contained bio-data information of respondents, while section B contained a 25-item statement to which respondents are expected to provide the correct answer by completing the gaps. PCSAT was validated by two experts from science education and one expert from measurement and evaluation from Benue State University, Makurdi. Corrections and suggestions arising from these experts were used to review the instrument before it was used. Cronbach Alpha was used to obtain the PCSAT reliability, which yielded a coefficient of 0.82. Mean and standard deviation scores were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses.

Results

Presentations in this section are based on research questions and hypotheses:

Research Question One

What is the difference in the mean skills acquisition scores between students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activities and those taught using discussion method? The answer to research question one is contained on Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Skills acquisition and Standard Deviation Scores of Students taught Physical Chemistry using Hands-on activities and Discussion Method.

Group	N	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST		Mean Gain
		$\bar{x}$	δ	$\bar{x}$	δ	
Hands-on Activities	77	11.72	1.10	26.20	1.73	14.48
Discussion	77	11.70	1.11	15.10	1.87	3.40
Mean difference		0.02		11.10		11.08

Source: Field Survey, 2017

Table 1 reveals that the pre-test and post-test mean skills acquisition scores difference for the two groups shows that students in the hands-on activity-based group had higher mean skills acquisition scores. There is also a positive difference of 11.08 between the post-test mean scores of the two groups in favour of the hands-on activities. This suggests that students taught using hands-on activities had higher skills acquisition in physical chemistry than their discussion group counterparts.

Research Question Two

What is the difference in the mean skills acquisition scores between male and female students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activities? The answer to research question two is presented on Table 2.

Table 2: Mean Skills acquisition and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students taught Physical Chemistry using Hands-on Activities

Sex	N	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST		Mean Gain
		$\bar{x}$	δ	$\bar{x}$	δ	
Male	40	10.83	1.17	21.38	1.86	10.55
Female	37	10.80	1.19	21.21	1.81	10.41
Mean difference		0.03		0.17		0.14

Source: Field Survey, 2017

Table 2 reveals that the mean difference of both sexes was 0.14. This difference though small is in favour of the male students. This implies that male students had slightly higher skills acquisition rate than their female counterparts in physical chemistry using hands-on activities.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean skills acquisition scores between students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activities and those taught using discussion method.

The answer to hypothesis one is presented in table 3

Table 3: ANCOVA Tests for Mean Skills acquisition Scores of Students taught Physical Chemistry using Hands-on activities and Discussion Method.

Source	Type III sum of square	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	<i>f</i>	Sig
Corrected model	1789.382a	2	425.093	145.811	.000
Intercept	1892.022	1	1892.022	569.071	.000
Pre-test	217.315	1	217.315	76.084	.000
Method	1994.228	1	1994.228	191.004	.000
Error	799.300	151	2.110		
Total	119306.010	154			
Corrected Total	2101.690	153			

a. R squared = .204 (Adjusted R Squared= .201)

Source: Field Survey, 2017

Table 3 reveals that there is a significant difference in the skills acquisition rating between hands-on activities and discussion methods of teaching in favour of hands-on activities [$F(1,153) = 191.004$, $P(0.0001 < 0.05)$]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that hands-on activities significantly enhanced students' skills acquisition in physical chemistry than discussion method.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean skills acquisition scores between male and female students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activities. The answer to hypothesis two is presented in table 4

Table 4: ANCOVA Tests for Mean Skills acquisition Scores of Male and Female Students taught Physical Chemistry using Hands-on Activities.

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected model	1224.400a	2	380.007	133.198	.000
Intercept	1030.801	1	1030.801	300.305	.000
Pre-test	171.118	1	171.118	104.809	.000
Gender	18.044	1	18.044	138.172	.071
Error	558.144	73	5.424		
Total	62084.100	76			
Corrected Total	440.009	75			

a. R squared = .185 (Adjusted R Squared= .161)

Table 4 reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean skills acquisition scores between male and female students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activities [$F(1,075) = 138.172$, $P(0.071 > 0.050)$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This means that hands-on activities significantly enhanced both male and female students' skills acquisition in physical chemistry

Discussion

The study examined the effects of hands-on activities on skill acquisition of senior secondary chemistry students in physical chemistry. Hands-on activities method of teaching was the independent variable. The results in table 1 revealed that the mean difference in skills acquisition score between hands-on activities group and discussion method group is 11.08 in favour of hands-on activities.

The result of hypothesis one indicated that there was a significant difference in the mean skill acquisition scores of students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activities and discussion methods in favour of hands-on activities. This supports earlier report by Ajayi (2016) who asserted that children learn best and acquire appropriate skills by doing not just by sitting and listening. Furthermore the findings of this study are in conformity with Omosewo (2016) who also affirmed that hands-on activities teaching featuring active students' participation in the learning process produces superior results than other methods. Hands-on activities method has great effects on students' skills acquisition in physical chemistry more so that it helps to practicalize those concepts in physical chemistry which are mostly abstract in nature in order to reduce them to concreteness or to reduce their degree of abstraction. In this way, students are motivated and materials are internalized more easily.

Another major finding in this study was that male students had slightly higher skills acquisition than their female counterparts using hands-on activities but ANCOVA test shows that the difference was no significant. This finding agrees with the findings of Eze (2010) and Al-Mustapha (2014) who found that there was no significant statistical difference on the skills acquisition of male and female students in Basic science. Based on this finding, skill acquisition in physical chemistry is therefore not dependent on gender. This means that the age long disparity in physical chemistry between male and female students can be laid to rest with the use of hands-on activities. However, the finding contradicts the finding of Abe (2011) who found gender disparity in students' skills acquisition in favour of female students in Biology.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is evident from the findings of this study that the use of hands-on activities could enhance student skills acquisition in physical chemistry regardless of gender. If hands-on activities proposed by this study is adopted in physical chemistry teaching and learning, it

will likely boost the skills acquisition of students. Based on the conclusion, the following recommendation is advised:

1. Hands-on activities should be encouraged to be used by chemistry teachers in teaching the physical chemistry in order to enhance students' skills acquisition in physical chemistry.
2. Hands-on activities require that, there should be standard laboratories and sufficient instructional materials. In this regard, Ministry of Education and schools administrators should provide standard laboratories and sufficient instructional materials for students to carryout necessary activities that could enhance skills acquisition in physical chemistry.

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